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AN EXPLORATORY STUDY OF SALES PROMOTION ACTIVITIES IN HAIR OIL CATEGORY: AN INSIGHT INTO CONSUMER AND RETAILER PERCEPTIONS

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ABSTRACT

In FMCG Product categories, it can be observed that two types of sales promotion schemes are very popular among the marketers is Price off and value added sales promotion schemes. Again in value added schemes free gift and % extra are widely used. This is applicable across International, National and Local brands of the FMCG. Furthermore from the point of views of consumer's benefits, there are immediate and delayed types of benefits offered by various sales promotion schemes. Among two types of benefits immediate benefits are widely used. While discussing with the experts and academician it is found that the medium through which sales promotion schemes awareness created among consumers also plays important role to prefer the particular sales promotion scheme.

In this paper, an attempt has been made to examine the nature of sales promotion activities in hair oil category in India, study retailer perceptions with respect to these activities and also get an insight into consumer perceptions of these activities. Our findings indicate that with respect to the nature of the schemes, premiums (free gifts) were found to be the most frequently used in both premium and popular toilet soap category, followed by price offs.

Key words: *FMCG, Consumer and Retailer Perceptions, Sales Promotion*

INTRODUCTION :

Understanding perceptions of channel members and consumers regarding sales promotion activities enhances the effectiveness of these activities. Widespread usage of sales promotion activities in Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) sector makes it imperative that manufacturers take into account channel member and consumer perceptions before planning such programmes. The importance of consumer sales promotion in the marketing mix of the fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) category throughout the world has increased. Companies spend considerable time in planning such activities. However, in order to enhance the effectiveness of these activities, manufacturers should understand consumer and retailer interpretations of their promotional activities. A study of these perceptions will reveal their preferences, their knowledge, and motivations. The study here pertains to consumers perceptions as well as retailer perceptions regarding sales promotion. Some past researches have suggested that promotion itself has an effect on the perceived value of the brand (1Cotton and Bobb 1978, Dodson, Tybout and Sternthal, 1978, Guadagni and Little 1983, Jones and Zufryden 1980, Rothschild and Gaidis 1981, Shoemaker and Shoaf 1977). This is because promotions provide utilitarian benefits such as monetary savings, added value, increased quality and convenience as well as hedonic benefits such as entertainment, exploration and self-expression (2Chandon, Laurent, and Waensink 1997).

Our study though exploratory has considered perceptions for price as well as non-price promotions in Hair oil category. The reasons for the study were:

- i) The widespread use of sales promotions in toilet soap category
- ii) Historically, whenever there was a downward trend in growth, sales promotion activities took the front seat of promotional mix.
- iii) Companies planned these activities with inward looking view hence it was felt that it would be useful to understand the perceptions of consumers and retailers regarding sales promotion activities to improve the effectiveness of these activities.

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Table-1: The Lead Players and their Market Share

Company	% of market share
Parachute	18
Hair & Care	14
Clinic All Clear	6
Dabur	30
Bajaj Almond Drops	20
Dabur Vatika	12

Source: Vanscom Database

The leading brands in the market are Coconut Oil, Advanced Ayurvedic, jasmine, DaburAnmol,Dabur Amla oils. A survey reported in Vanscom, which was conducted in Bareilly, showed that 13 Hair oil brands were available in this city alone. The industry had witnessed many innovative sales promotion activities in the recent past. Numerous factors were responsible for such a phenomenon. One of the reasons being that the market being sluggish, companies were trying to increase market share in stagnant to declining (volume terms) market in order to retain consumers, to encourage switching, to induce trials and liquidate excessive inventories. Another reason possible was that with the presence of so many brands the competition had increased severally leading to fight for market share and shelf space. Inflationary trend had made both the consumer as well as trade deal prone. Hence, sales promotion activities in hair oil industry posed a very interesting study and consumer and retailer perceptions thereof. On the basis of information collected on various brands and their prices, following three segments emerge.

Table-2: Price Segments of Hair oil

Segment	Price	Weight
Premium	> Rs.90	100 ml
Popular	Rs.40	100ml.
Economy	< Rs.27	100ml.

The brands in popular segments were found to be frequently promoted as there was intensive price competition in this segment. The brands could also be classified based on medicinal benefits, cosmetic benefits, perfumes, natural/herbal properties. For the purpose of this study, only price segments were considered

Review of literature:

An attempt has been made to pursue the literature of earlier studies. Lot of studies has been conducted consumer satisfaction and consumer attitude towards FMCG products. FMCG products are the day-to-day usage of millions of people. A study on impact on buying on FMCG products helps to millions of people how they are utilizing and how they opined about it. For the purpose of review, some studies conducted on satisfaction and attitude towards FMCG products are studied.

Manohar U. Kalwani and Chi Kin Yim (1992) found that the brands expected price is a linear function of the price promotion frequency and the depth of price discounts at conventional significance levels. Nevertheless, the results provide some directional support for nonlinear relationships between the expected price and two elements of a price promotion schedule. Given the important implications of such potential nonlinear effects of price promotions on brands' expected prices, further research testing those nonlinear effects of price promotions should prove fruitful for the design of optimal price promotion policies. They also contributed that promotion expectations suggest that unfulfilled promotion expectation events among consumers who have come to expect promotions on a brand because of frequent exposure to them will have an adverse impact on the brand. Analogously, unexpected promotion events will enhance the probability of purchasing a brand among consumers who have not been exposed to many price promotions and therefore do not as a rule expect the brand

to be available on a promotional deal. They suggest that those results are consistent with the rational expectations view that "any policy rule that is systematically related to economic conditions.

Davis (2002) adds that brands should be managed as assets using a top down approach where senior executives embrace the concept that marketing should have a leading seat at the strategy table and use the brands to drive key strategic decisions. Also if senior executives are vocal and show commitment to the brands, then employees within an organization will start taking ownership of the brand.

Verstraeten, D Van den Poel, A Prinzie & P Van Kenhove (2002) stated in their study that in the marketing domain, sequential patterns have been usefully deployed for predicting various aspects of customer purchase behavior. Hence, the goal of this paper was to introduce a new concept that might prove to be a relevant tool for marketing decision making rather than offering a sound solution within a clearly demarcated problem definition. As opposed to the traditional sequence-analysis approaches, in this study, an array of binary logit analyses was applied for detecting significant sequences among category purchases. In summary, it shows that (i) binary log analysis provides a feasible alternative for detecting and selecting highly significant sequential relationships, (ii) a sequential architecture can be successfully compiled through the methodology offered in this paper, and (iii) the provided sequential architecture can be a useful tool in understanding and predicting customer behavior. Future applications possibly lie ahead in the field of inter-category management, shelf-space allocation, store-layout decisions, retailer promotions, customer profiling and individual customer predictions.

Objectives:

The main objectives of the study are:

- to assess current consumer sales promotion schemes in Hair oil market
- to get an insight into retailers' views regarding the schemes being offered in hair oil category, and consumer perceptions
- to study consumer perceptions regarding various schemes in this category and responses toward them.

Methodology:

In order to address the above questions an exploratory study was conducted. The idea was to probe and get deeper insight into sales promotion scenario in hair oil market and to tap perceptions of retailers and consumers.

In order to address above mentioned objectives

- (i) study of secondary sources was carried out,
- (ii) in-depth interview of eight retailers was undertaken and
- (iii) structured questionnaire was designed to seek consumer responses.

Convenience sampling was used for both retailers as well as consumer studies. eight retailers ranging from small kirana store to supermarket were approached. All the retailers were located in the bareilly city *. The respondents for consumer study were postgraduate students in the age group of 19-24 belonging to middle and upper middle and upper class. The total respondents were 30 in number. They were residing in hostel and hence sole decision-makers for this category. Also this age-group being more experimental and likely to be more deal prone, so their perceptions, preferences would give some insights to companies planning sales promotions targetted at them. Content analysis of 28 schemes an illustrative sample of schemes offered during last one year was done. The sources of the information of these schemes were:

- i) 12 www.agencyfaqs.com, and
- ii) print advertisements making announcements of the schemes.

In-depth interviews of retailers were conducted with the help of interview guide. Inferences were drawn from that. In case of consumer study with the help of structured questionnaire, simple frequency analysis and cross tabulations were carried out and inferences were drawn.

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Analysis:

1. Study on Retailer Perceptions

- Perceptions on Scheme Preference
- Perception about Buying Roles
- Perceptions about Response to Sales Promotion Offers
- Perceptions about Communications of Sales Promotion Schemes
- Dealer-Retailer Dynamics
- Margins
- Perceptions about terms and conditions
- Nature of POP
- Servicing during duration of Scheme
- Gifts for Retailer motivation
- Handling Problems

2. Reasons for switching brands:

Reasons	No.of people
Variety/Boredom	10
Availability	3
Packaging/Novelty/Features	1
Price	3
Sales Promotion	1
Advertising	6
Impulse	4
Do not change	8

As obvious from the above table, sales promotion was not the main reason for switching brand in this category. Need for variety was the predominant reason. It was found through deeper probing that even though consumers would have switched brands due to sales promotion, there was reluctance about admitting the same and variety was given as a reason for switching. It was further found that consumers had positive disposition towards promoted brand. As a result when toilet soap brand was changed for variety, the brand which was promoted had higher probability of purchase than non-promoted brands.

3.Willingness to buy on sales promotion offer

Sixty-three per cent of the sample did not show willingness to buy a brand due to promotion while 27% showed willingness and 10% were not sure. This indicates that when 27% showed willingness, and 10% consumers who were not sure, these groups might be lured through innovative and lucrative sales promotion offer.

Conclusion:

The findings exhibited that both the retailers and consumers perceived that sales promotion activities carried out by the companies for increasing sales in short term and clearing excess stocks. What it implies is that companies need to use sales promotion synergistically and communicate so that they provide value to the target audience and enhance brand quality/image perceptions. Companies need to systematise information flow regarding sales promotion activities particularly at dealer retailer level. Ensuring proper information flow and devising checks and to reduce misappropriations and implementation flows should be considered critical aspects for the success of sales promotion activities by the companies. As retailing is fragmented, direct reach by companies is next to impossible. Through dealers and proper feedback mechanism, companies keep in touch with the market. From the study it was found that smaller retailers felt neglected and not enthused to implement the schemes, particularly when additional handling, stocking, accounting was required on the part of a retailer without compensatory margins.

Suggestions:

The time period of a quarter is another limitation as it only gives a snapshot of activities undertaken over the year. The schemes compiled are also not representative of the categories in practice. Hence, generalizations drawn would have to be viewed keeping in mind the above limitations. If such a study is done over a few years, trends can be analysed. Linking the incentive to the outcome-sales would provide a better understanding of the rationale for designing promotions. If consumers tend to perceive various offers as similar for brands of their consideration set, either they may buy only the promoted brand or may not respond to promotion. In case of new brand introduction in any category, it is not necessary that the new brand has to offer a higher level of incentive as found in this study. Thus, several factors need to be considered before determining the size of incentive to be offered to consumers such as level of competition, available budget for the brand, reputation of the company introducing a brand, consumer behaviour, competitive promotional offers, level of price of a brand *vis-à-vis* competition.

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